

Corporate Governance, Product Market Competition, and Firm Value: A Cross Economy Analysis of Developed, Developing and Emerging Economies

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of corporate governance mechanisms and product market competition on firm value across developed, developing, and emerging economies. The study employs pooled OLS, fixed-effects, and random-effects models to identify variations across economic contexts. Across all contexts, product market competition consistently enhances firm value, with the most substantial effect observed in emerging economies, highlighting its role in fostering market discipline. This study contributes to the literature by addressing gaps in understanding the early detection of overvaluation and by situating the governance-performance relationship within varying institutional settings. It extends the theory of disruptive innovation by integrating regulatory and competitive environments into governance analysis. The findings offer practical implications for policymakers and firms seeking to improve governance structures and competitive positioning across different economic landscapes.

Keywords: *Corporate governance, Product market competition, firm value.*

JEL Classification codes: *G34, L11, G32, L25, O16, G38, L40, O43.*

Suggested citation: Ali, M., Hassan, A.U., Tehseen, S., Naeem, E., & Abbas, R. (2026). Corporate Governance, Product Market Competition, and Firm Value: A Cross Economy Analysis of Developed, Developing and Emerging Economies. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 3(1), 100-112. DOI: 10.59324/ejmecb.2026.3(1).08

Introduction

This study explores how corporate governance mechanisms and product market competition influence firm valuation, particularly within the context of equity overvaluation. Previous research has extensively examined the relationship between corporate governance structures and firm performance, with findings generally indicating a positive association (Donaldson & Davis, 1991; Coles et al., 2001).

Effective governance is essential for building investor confidence and fostering trust in regulatory institutions particularly relevant for Pakistan's corporate sector, where transparent governance frameworks are increasingly critical (Hassan et al., 2025). Furthermore, existing literature suggests that product market competition may act as a substitute for governance structures in mitigating agency problems (Ammann et al., 2013; Giroud & Mueller, 2011). However, the degree to which this substitution is effective depends heavily on the strength of investor protection mechanisms. In environments where investor safeguards are weak, the complementary role of market competition becomes more valuable. Conversely, in jurisdictions with robust investor protections, the marginal benefit of governance or competition is diminished due to existing institutional safeguards.

Agency problems are exacerbated in weak governance environments, increasing the likelihood of value-destroying behaviors (Healy & Palepu, 2001). Product market competition influences managerial behavior by reshaping the structure of agency costs and disclosure incentives (Hoberg & Phillips, 2010). Measured using the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), competitive intensity serves as a disciplinary force, compelling managers to prioritize firm value (Chen et al., 2014).

While the interaction between corporate governance and product market competition has received limited empirical attention, theoretical frameworks from economics and accounting provide insights into how competitive dynamics may either alleviate or intensify agency conflicts (Khajavi et al., 2023). Prior studies highlight the potential of product market competition to enhance internal supervision and managerial accountability (Scharfstein, 1988)

Methodologically, the study employs refined proxies for governance including board size, board independence, and gender diversity and competition, using HHI and leverage ratios. These are supplemented by macroeconomic controls such as GDP growth and inflation. Firm size, measured via total assets, serves as the valuation metric. By analyzing data across 15 countries classified into developed, developing, and emerging economies, this research captures the institutional heterogeneity necessary for a comprehensive cross-contextual analysis.

This research offers multiple contributions: it identifies the antecedents of equity overvaluation, offering predictive guidance for investors and regulators; highlights the synergistic role of governance and competition in preserving firm value; and provides empirical validation of the governance potential of female directors. By bridging gaps in the literature and proposing actionable strategies, this study advances both academic understanding and practical governance frameworks for maintaining sustainable firm valuation in volatile markets.

Literature Review

Corporate Governance and Firm Value

The need for robust corporate governance (CG) practices becomes particularly important in contexts where investor trust and regulatory oversight are underdeveloped, as is often the case in Pakistan's corporate landscape (Hassan et al., 2025). Board composition and ownership structure are two critical elements of CG that influence how firms are directed and controlled, thereby

affecting overall performance. Jensen and Meckling (1976) emphasized that managerial ownership could serve as an incentive alignment tool, thereby reducing agency conflicts.

Female directors tend to demonstrate greater engagement in board activities, as evidenced by higher levels of preparedness (Pathan & Faff, 2013) and more frequent attendance at board meetings (Adams & Ferreira, 2009). Such active participation enhances board oversight, which is generally associated with improved organizational performance. Furthermore, from the perspective of resource dependency theory, the presence of female board members introduces valuable resources and diverse external connections, thereby enriching the board's strategic capacity and access to critical information.

Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis are proposed:

H1: There is a negative and statistically significant relationship between board size and firm value.

H2: There is a negative and significant relation between independent director and firm value.

H3: There is a positive and significant relation between female director and firm value.

Product Market Competition and Firm Value

Product market competition is closely linked with allocative efficiency and productivity improvements. In competitive environments, firms are driven to offer goods and services at the lowest sustainable cost, thereby aligning market prices more accurately with the intrinsic value of products.

In quantifying product market competition, the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) is widely used to measure industry concentration. A higher HHI denotes a more concentrated market and, therefore, lower competitive intensity. Following Chen et al. (2014), this study measures competition as ONE_HHI, calculated as one minus the HHI, where ONE_HHI_{jt} represents the competitive intensity in industry j at time t.

$$ONE_{HHI} = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} \left[\frac{sales_{ijt}}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} sales_{ijt}} \right]^2 \quad (1)$$

The Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) is a widely utilized indicator of market concentration, particularly relevant in the context of assessing competitiveness before and after mergers and acquisitions. Accordingly, the underlying hypothesis posited by this metric is:

H4: there is positive and significant relationship between HHI and total assets.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Methodology

This study employs a comparative research design to investigate the influence of corporate governance and product market competition on firm valuation across a diverse set of developed, developing, and emerging economies. Spanning the period from 2010 to 2019, the analysis utilizes panel data to account for both temporal dynamics and cross-national differences. Firm valuation, proxied by total assets, serves as the primary dependent variable. Data are sourced from 15 countries, equally divided into five developed, five developing, and five emerging economies.

Measurement of variables

Corporate Governance

It is an independent variable and research aligns with the stream of multi-country governance prediction studies, such as those conducted by 20 (Durnev & Kim, 2005), (Klapper & Love, Gillan S.L., Hartzell, J.C., Starks, L.T., 2004). (Durnev & Kim, 2005) present a conceptual framework in which firms aiming to raise capital are incentivized to enhance their corporate governance practices.

Board Size

Jensen (1994) posits that smaller boards tend to exercise more effective oversight of CEOs, attributing this to the reduced emphasis on formality and social decorum that often characterizes larger boards traits which can enable CEOs to exert greater influence. Similarly, Yermack (1996) finds that firms with smaller boards exhibit stronger governance outcomes, supporting the notion that board size plays a significant role in monitoring effectiveness.

Independent Directors

The findings revealed a mixed relationship between the proportion of independent directors and firm performance. Despite some firms having a higher representation of independent directors, this did not necessarily translate into improved performance outcomes (Liu et al., 2015). The board of directors' functions as a collective decision-making body tasked with safeguarding shareholder interests.

Female Directors

Women play a significant role in enhancing board governance. Empirical evidence indicates that gender-diverse boards are more proactive in holding CEOs accountable for underperformance, as CEO turnover tends to be more responsive to stock return declines in firms with a higher proportion of female directors. Notably, this effect appears stronger and more consistent than the influence of board independence on CEO turnover, as previously observed by Weisbach (1988). In evaluating board effectiveness, committee membership is used as a proxy for active involvement in governance.

Product Market Competition

Product market competition is treated as an independent variable in this study. Consistent with previous research (e.g., Cheng et al., 2013), two key proxies are employed to capture market competition: the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index (HHI) and the Market Size Index. The HHI is a widely recognized indicator of market concentration, calculated by summing the squares of each firm's market share within a given industry. Following the methodology proposed by Chen et al. (2014), this study adopts an alternative measure of competition, denoted as ONE_HHI, which is defined as one minus the HHI value. ONE_HHI_{jt} represents the level of product market competition for firms operating in industry j during year t .

Empirical Model

The general form is under:

$$FV = f(CG_{it} + PMC_{it} + CI_{it}) \quad (2)$$

This equation shows the firm value is function of independent variables. FV= represent firm value, CG =represents corporate governance, PMC= represents product market competition, and CI = represents control variable i =country effects t= time period.

Here the relationship of estimation model energetic panel would use,

$$FV = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_1(CG)_{it} + \sum \beta_2(PMC)_{it} + \sum \beta_3 X_{it} + \mu_{it} + \vartheta_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

In equation two, X_{it} is the variable, which denotes control variable which is for the consisting for the vector gross domestic product development, and firm size, all are the control variables. In addition, μ_i is the representation of the effects of panel level, β_t representation of effect of the time, finally ϑ_{it} and ε_{it} denote the error terms.

In our research additional models have empirical for interaction of governance mechanism, product market competition and firm value given below.

$$FV = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_1 (BS)_{it} + \sum \beta_2 (ID)_{it} + \sum \beta_3 (FD)_{it} + \sum \beta_4 (1 - HHI)_{it} + \mu_{it} + \vartheta_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

“i” is the effect of the country, and “t” is the time frame.

Table 1. Definition of Variables

Variable	Type of Variable	Proxy	Definition
Corporate Governance (CG)	Independent Variable	Board size (BS)	Total number of board of directors (BOD)
		Independent Director (ID)	Total number of independent directors from BOD
		Female Director	Total number of female directors from BOD
Product Market Competition (PMC)	Independent Variable	HHI	Market share of each firm in the industry, squaring them and summing the result
Firm Value (FV)	Dependent Variable	Total Assets	It is measured with the total asset of a firm
Inflation	Control Variable	Inflation rate	Annually Inflation rate of each country
GDP	Control Variable	GDP growth rate	Annually GDP growth of each country

Empirical Results

This study analyzes data from fifteen countries, categorized into three groups: five developed, five developing, and five emerging economies. The objective is to investigate how corporate governance and product market competition influence firm performance across diverse economic

contexts. To begin the empirical analysis, we present results derived from cross-sectional Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regressions. These initial regressions are conducted without controlling for potential endogeneity issues. The primary aim of this step is to establish that firm performance, market competition, and corporate governance mechanisms exhibit statistically significant relationships, even within a basic OLS framework.

Descriptive Summary

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the variables employed in the study. The average value of total assets (5.82) indicates that the sample predominantly comprises medium- to large-sized firms. In terms of board characteristics, the mean board size of 10.44 members is typical for firms operating in regulated industries. The average number of independent directors (4.22) reflects a moderate level of compliance with corporate governance practices. Furthermore, the mean number of female directors (1.18) underscores the persistence of gender disparities in corporate leadership. The average product market competition score, measured using the ONE-HHI index (31.31), suggests a moderately competitive landscape.

Regarding macroeconomic control variables, the average GDP growth rate (0.03) and inflation rate (0.039) indicate a stable economic climate during the study period. The standard deviation values reveal the degree of variability across the dataset. Total assets demonstrate moderate dispersion (SD = 1.91). Among governance-related metrics, board size exhibits the highest variability (SD = 4.14), followed by independent directors (SD = 3.36) and female directors (SD = 1.29). Product market competition, reflected by the ONE-HHI index, also shows substantial variation (SD = 6.77), corroborating the industry-level differences in competition identified. The macroeconomic variables, GDP growth rate (SD = 0.032) and inflation rate (SD = 0.033), exhibit minimal variability, reinforcing the notion of economic stability, which is crucial for isolating firm-specific influences in cross-sectional research designs.

Table 2. Descriptive Summary

Variables	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Independent director	4.22	3.36	0	16
Female director	1.18	1.29	0	7
Board size	10.44	4.14	4	26
PMC	31.31	6.77	5.75	46.05
Total assets	5.82	1.91	2.13	11.89
Inflation	0.039	0.033	0.0001	0.16
GDP	0.036	0.032	0.0002	0.25

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis assesses the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables, with values ranging from +1 (indicating a perfect positive correlation) to -1 (indicating a perfect negative correlation), while a value of 0 denotes no linear association. [Table 3](#) presents the correlation matrix based on 2,998 firm-level observations. The matrix provides insights into the relationships between various proxies of corporate governance, product market competition, and firm size, represented by total assets.

The results reveal a mixed pattern of associations. Among governance-related variables, total assets are negatively correlated with board size ($r = -0.093$), suggesting that larger firms tend to have slightly smaller boards. A stronger negative correlation is observed between total assets and the proportion of independent directors ($r = -0.23$), as well as with female board representation ($r = -$

0.13). These findings imply that increases in firm size may not necessarily correspond with greater board independence or gender diversity.

Conversely, a strong positive correlation is identified between total assets and product market competition, as measured by ONE-HHI ($r = 0.73$), indicating that larger firms are more likely to operate in competitive market environments. Regarding macroeconomic control variables, total assets show a modest positive correlation with GDP growth ($r = 0.14$) and a moderate positive correlation with inflation ($r = 0.27$), suggesting that firm size tends to increase in relatively expanding or inflationary economic conditions.

These correlations offer preliminary insights into the potential relationships among the study variables and provide a basis for further regression analysis.

Table 3. Correlation Analysis

Variable	BS	ID	FD	PMC	TA	GDP	Inflation
Board size	1						
Independent Director	0.58	1					
Female Director	0.25	0.27	1				
PMC	-0.094	-0.19	-0.12	1			
Total Assets	-0.093	-0.23	-0.13	0.73	1		
GDP	-0.016	0.05	0.02	0.09	0.14	1	
Inflation	-0.049	-0.24	-0.23	0.25	0.27	0.0004	1

Regression Analysis for Corporate Governance and Total Assets

The relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and firm size, proxied by total assets, was examined using three econometric approaches: Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Fixed Effects (FE), and Random Effects (RE) models. The results reveal differentiated associations, highlighting the significance of model selection when analyzing governance-related dynamics.

Board size demonstrates varying effects across models. In the OLS regression, it shows a positive and statistically significant relationship with total assets ($\beta = 0.0286$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that larger boards may facilitate access to diverse resources and enhance strategic capacity at a cross-sectional level. However, this association turns negative in both FE ($\beta = -0.0037$, $p < 0.1$) and RE models ($\beta = -0.0005$, $p < 0.1$), implying that, over time, larger boards might reduce decision-making efficiency within firms. Similarly, the presence of independent directors is negatively associated with firm size in all models, though the magnitude and significance differ. The OLS model indicates a strong negative relationship ($\beta = -0.167$, $p < 0.01$), which weakens under the FE specification ($\beta = -0.018$, $p < 0.1$) and becomes moderately significant in the RE model ($\beta = -0.035$, $p < 0.05$).

In contrast, female board representation displays a reversal across models. While the OLS results indicate a negative relationship with firm size ($\beta = -0.068$, $p < 0.05$), the FE ($\beta = 0.099$, $p < 0.01$) and RE models ($\beta = 0.089$, $p < 0.01$) show a strong and significant positive association. Control variables also reflect model sensitivity. GDP growth and inflation rates are positively related to firm size in the OLS model (GDP: $\beta = 9.375$, $p < 0.01$; inflation: $\beta = 12.26$, $p < 0.01$), reflecting broader cross-country macroeconomic trends. However, these relationships reverse in the FE and RE models (GDP: $\beta = -1.857$, $p < 0.01$; inflation: $\beta = -2.882$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that within-firm variations capture the adverse effects of inflation on real asset values and economic volatility more accurately. The higher explanatory power of the OLS model ($R^2 = 13.1\%$) compared to the FE model ($R^2 = 2.9\%$) suggests that much of the variation in firm size is driven by cross-sectional rather than temporal differences.

Overall, these findings highlight the complex and context-dependent nature of corporate governance's influence on firm value. They suggest that policymakers and corporate leaders, especially in emerging economies, should tailor governance reforms to reflect institutional realities, recognizing that the impact of board structure is not uniform but sensitive to both methodological approach and economic context.

Table 4. Regression Analysis for Corporate Governance and Total Assets

Variable	(1) OLS	(2) FE	(3) RE
Board size	0.0286** -0.0116	-0.00371* -0.0106	-0.000510* -0.0103
Independent Director	-0.167*** -0.0178	-0.0182* -0.0151	-0.0357** -0.0148
Female Director	-0.0680** -0.028	0.0997*** -0.0194	0.0897*** -0.0192
GDP	9.375*** -0.993	-1.857*** -0.427	-1.589*** -0.431
Inflation	12.26*** -1.037	-2.882*** -0.542	-2.284*** -0.544
Constant	5.479*** -0.117	5.994*** -0.0945	6.013*** -0.133
Observations	2998	2998	2998
R Square	0.131	0.029	
No of IDs		300	300
<i>Standard errors are in parentheses</i>			
<i>***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1</i>			

Hausman test for Corporate Governance and Total Assets

Table 5 reports the results of the Hausman specification test, which compares the fixed effects (FE) and random effects (RE) models in evaluating the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and firm size, proxied by total assets. This test determines whether unobserved firm-specific characteristics are correlated with the explanatory variables an essential consideration for selecting an appropriate panel data model. The test statistic ($\chi^2(5) = 60.86, p = 0.00$) strongly rejects the null hypothesis that RE is consistent and efficient, thereby endorsing the fixed effects model as the more reliable specification.

The fixed effects estimates indicate a negative relationship between board size ($\beta = -0.003$) and firm size, as well as a similarly negative association for independent directors ($\beta = -0.01$). These findings contrast with the random effects model, where independent directors show a positive coefficient ($\beta = 0.03$), likely reflecting omitted variable bias in the RE specification. Female board representation exhibits a consistent positive relationship with total assets across both models (FE: $\beta = 0.09$; RE: $\beta = 0.08$), suggesting that gender diversity exerts a stable and beneficial influence on firm value.

Table 5. Hausman Test for Corporate Governance and Total Assets

Variable	(b)FE	(b)RE	DF	SE
Board size	-0.003	0	0	0
Independent Director	-0.01	0.03	0.01	0
Female Director	0.09	0.08	0.01	0
GDP	-1.85	-1.58	-0.26	-

Inflation	-2.88	-2.28	-0.59	-
Chi (5) = 60.86				
Pro<chi=0.00				

Regression Analysis for Product Market Competition and Total Assets

Table 6 examines the impact of product market competition measured through the ONE-HHI index, where higher values denote greater market concentration on firm size, proxied by total assets. The analysis employs three econometric approaches: Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Fixed Effects (FE), and Random Effects (RE), highlighting the influence of methodological choice on inference.

The findings indicate a consistent and statistically significant positive relationship between market concentration and total assets across all model specifications. In the OLS model, a strong coefficient ($\beta = 0.198$, $SE = 0.004$, $p < 0.01$) suggests that firms operating in less competitive, more concentrated industries tend to accumulate more assets. Although the magnitude of this relationship diminishes in panel data models, it remains significant FE ($\beta = 0.117$, $SE = 0.005$) and RE ($\beta = 0.138$, $SE = 0.005$) demonstrating the robustness of the association after accounting for unobserved firm-specific characteristics.

Macroeconomic control variables exhibit model-dependent behavior. The OLS results reveal positive relationships between total assets and both GDP growth ($\beta = 4.843$, $SE = 0.715$) and inflation ($\beta = 5.459$, $SE = 0.727$), which likely reflect broader cross-country economic trends. In contrast, FE and RE models show negative coefficients for GDP growth (FE: $\beta = -1.519$, $SE = 0.395$) and inflation (FE: $\beta = -2.751$, $SE = 0.495$), emphasizing that within-firm variations suggest macroeconomic instability may undermine asset accumulation. The Hausman test ($\chi^2(5) = 60.86$, $p = 0.00$) confirms the preference for the fixed effects model over random effects. While OLS yields a higher explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.55$), this likely captures between-firm variation, whereas FE's lower R^2 (0.168) reflects its focus on within-firm dynamics.

Table 6. Regression Analysis for Total Assets and Product Market Competition

Variable	(1) OLS	(2) FE	(3) RE
ONE_HHI	0.198*** -0.0036	0.117*** -0.00532	0.138*** -0.0048
GDP	4.843*** -0.715	-1.519*** -0.395	-1.118*** -0.398
Inflation	5.459*** -0.727	-2.751*** -0.495	-1.976*** -0.493
Constant	1.211*** -0.0803	3.487*** -0.118	2.989*** -0.126
Observations	2998	2998	2998
R Square	0.55	0.168	
No of IDs		300	300

Note: Standard errors are in parentheses; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Hausman Test for Total Assets and Product Market Competition

The Hausman test was employed to determine the most appropriate econometric model fixed effects (FE) versus random effects (RE) for assessing the relationship between product market competition (proxied by ONE-HHI), macroeconomic indicators (GDP growth and inflation), and firm-level total assets. The test produced a highly significant result ($\chi^2(3) = 409.02$, $p = 0.00$),

rejecting the null hypothesis that RE estimates are consistent and efficient. This finding affirms the validity of the fixed effects model in capturing firm- or country-specific. For product market competition, both FE and RE models yield positive coefficients FE: $\beta = 0.11$; RE: $\beta = 0.13$ implying that firms operating in more concentrated markets tend to possess larger asset bases. However, the smaller magnitude of the FE coefficient ($\Delta = -0.02$) suggests that RE models may overstate this effect by failing to account for unobserved contextual factors, such as regulatory strictness or industry-specific barriers.

In the case of GDP growth, both models report negative relationships with total assets (FE: $\beta = -1.51$; RE: $\beta = -1.11$), consistent with the notion that economic growth. The more pronounced effect in the FE model ($\Delta = -0.40$) underscores the importance of controlling for latent structural differences across firms or countries.

Inflation also exhibits a stronger negative impact in the fixed effects model ($\beta = -2.75$) than in the random effects model ($\beta = -1.97$), with a sizable difference ($\Delta = -0.77$). This indicates that inflation's erosion of real asset values is more accurately captured when unobserved firm-level characteristics are controlled for, reinforcing the case for FE estimation in inflation-sensitive analyses.

The uniform direction and significance of the coefficient differences ONE-HHI ($\Delta = -0.02$), GDP growth ($\Delta = -0.40$), and inflation ($\Delta = -0.77$) highlight a systematic bias in RE estimates due to their inability to address endogeneity arising from correlated omitted variables. In light of these findings, researchers and policymakers should prioritize fixed effects specifications to ensure robust inference in studies of firm performance, particularly when investigating environments characterized by high levels of structural and institutional heterogeneity.

Table 7. Hausman Test for Total Assets and Product Market Competition

Variable	(b) FE	(b) re	DF	SE
ONE_HHI	0.11	0.13	-0.02	0
GDP	-1.51	-1.11	-0.4	
Inflation	-2.75	-1.97	-0.77	0.04

Discussion

This research examines the influence of corporate governance mechanisms and product market competition on firm value. To assess these relationships, we employ pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), fixed effects (FE), and random effects (RE) regression models. The findings reveal that fixed effects provide more robust estimations, emphasizing the critical role of unobserved heterogeneity in analyzing governance and competition dynamics.

Our first hypothesis posits a significant negative relationship between board size and total assets. This outcome is consistent with prior studies (Guest, 2009; Ahmed Sheikh et al., 2013), suggesting that excessively large boards may contribute to inefficiencies in governance, leading to suboptimal utilization of corporate resources.

The second hypothesis explores the role of independent directors, hypothesizing a negative association with total assets. This finding aligns with Chen et al. (2018), who report that greater board independence often correlates with more conservative decision-making in emerging markets. Independent directors, those unaffiliated with a firm's management or daily operations are intended to provide objective oversight.

Our third hypothesis examines the impact of gender diversity, proposing a positive relationship between female board representation and total assets. The results affirm this hypothesis, suggesting that the inclusion of women on corporate boards contributes positively to firm value.

The fourth hypothesis addresses the connection between product market competition, measured through the inverse Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (ONE-HHI), and total assets. The analysis finds a positive and significant relationship, indicating that firms operating in more concentrated markets (higher ONE-HHI) tend to accumulate greater assets. This result resonates with the insights of Laeven and Levine (2008), who suggest that concentrated market structures facilitate strategic investments in asset-intensive projects due to better coordination and access to capital.

The study incorporates two macroeconomic control variables: GDP growth and inflation. Both exhibit negative relationships with total assets, particularly when considered in the context of corporate governance. These results suggest that macroeconomic volatility can adversely affect asset accumulation. Specifically, in the context of product market competition, GDP growth demonstrates an insignificant negative relationship with total assets, implying that firm-level asset expansion may not always align with broader economic trends in emerging economies.

Conclusion

This study explores the influence of corporate governance mechanisms and product market competition on firm value by employing pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression alongside fixed and random effects models to account for unobserved heterogeneity. By testing four distinct hypotheses, the research contributes to the ongoing discourse on governance efficiency and market dynamics, offering practical recommendations for both corporate leaders and policy stakeholders. The key empirical findings, interpreted within established theoretical and empirical frameworks, are summarized as follows.

First, the inverse relationship observed between board size and total assets lends support to agency theory (Jensen, 1994) and is consistent with prior empirical research (Guest, 2009; Ahmed Sheikh et al., 2013). Larger boards may impede effective governance by introducing coordination challenges and decision-making delays, ultimately leading to inefficient asset allocation. This suggests that firms should prioritize governance quality over board size, favoring leaner and more agile boards that can make timely and effective strategic decisions.

Second, the negative correlation between the proportion of independent directors and firm assets challenges the prevailing assumption that board independence uniformly enhances firm performance. This finding aligns with literature from emerging markets and critiques of excessive board independence (Bhagat & Black, 2002), indicating that overly independent boards may lack the contextual and strategic acumen required for making complex, asset-related decisions. Thus, firms should aim for a balanced board composition that combines independent oversight with domain-specific knowledge and expertise.

Third, the study finds a positive and significant association between female board representation and total assets, supporting the resource dependency theory. This theory posits that diverse leadership brings varied perspectives and capabilities that enhance strategic planning and innovation (Post & Byron, 2015). These findings are in line emphasize the value of gender diversity in improving asset utilization and strategic growth, particularly in rapidly evolving market environments. This suggests that inclusive governance structures can contribute meaningfully to firm performance and should be actively promoted.

Finally, a positive relationship between market concentration measured by the inverse Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (ONE-HHI) and total assets highlights the strategic advantages enjoyed by firms

in less competitive markets. This supports the view that concentrated market environments facilitate more decisive management and improved access to capital, enabling investment in asset-heavy initiatives such as mergers, research and development, or infrastructure expansion. These findings are consistent with the work of Laeven and Levine (2008) and Holderness (2003), and they echo Schumpeterian arguments that moderate market power can promote innovation and growth through scale advantages (Schumpeter, 2021).

Theoretical and Practical Contribution

The findings of this study contribute to bridging corporate governance theory with strategic business practices. For regulators in emerging markets, policy measures such as promoting gender quotas and enhancing transparency in ownership structures could help foster more competitive and accountable corporate environments. Nonetheless, this study is not without limitations. Relying on total assets as a proxy for firm value may fail to capture intangible drivers of performance or long-term sustainability. Future research could benefit from employing alternative indicators such as Tobin's Q or environmental, social, and governance (ESG) metrics to provide a more nuanced understanding of firm valuation.

In conclusion, the study affirms that corporate governance and market competition function not as isolated determinants but as interrelated influences on firm value. Aligning internal governance mechanisms with external market conditions can enhance strategic resource allocation and support long-term, sustainable corporate growth.

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